

IPBES TCA Chapter 4. Review of literature on institutional misfits and inadequate policies / IPBES transformative change assessment

First 50 records screened in second search on institutional fit and spatial fit

- Acton, Leslie, Rebecca L Gruby, and others. 2021. "Does Polycentricity Fit? Linking Social Fit with Polycentric Governance in a Large-Scale Marine Protected Area." *Journal of Environmental Management* 290: 112613.
- Alexander, Steven M, Derek Armitage, Peter J Carrington, and Örjan Bodin. 2017. "Examining Horizontal and Vertical Social Ties to Achieve Social–Ecological Fit in an Emerging Marine Reserve Network." *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 27 (6): 1209–23.
- Anderies, John M, and Marco A Janssen. 2013. "Robustness of Social-Ecological Systems: Implications for Public Policy." *Policy Studies Journal* 41 (3): 513–36.
- Armitage, Derek, Chris Béné, Anthony T Charles, Derek Johnson, and Edward H Allison. 2012. "The Interplay of Well-Being and Resilience in Applying a Social-Ecological Perspective." *Ecology and Society* 17 (4).
- Barnes, Michele L, Örjan Bodin, Angela M Guerrero, Ryan RJ McAllister, Steven M Alexander, and Garry Robins. 2017. "The Social Structural Foundations of Adaptation and Transformation in Social–Ecological Systems." *Ecology and Society* 22 (4).
- Barnes, Michele L, Örjan Bodin, Tim R McClanahan, John N Kittinger, Andrew S Hoey, Orou G Gaoue, and Nicholas AJ Graham. 2019. "Social-Ecological Alignment and Ecological Conditions in Coral Reefs." *Nature Communications* 10 (1): 2039.
- Bergsten, Arvid, Diego Galafassi, and Örjan Bodin. 2014. "The Problem of Spatial Fit in Social-Ecological Systems: Detecting Mismatches between Ecological Connectivity and Land Management in an Urban Region." *Ecology and Society* 19 (4).
- Boakye-Danquah, John, Maureen G Reed, James P Robson, and Tetsu Sato. 2018. "A Problem of Social Fit? Assessing the Role of Bridging Organizations in the Recoupling of Socio-Ecological Systems." *Journal of Environmental Management* 223: 338–47.
- Bodin, Örjan. 2017. "Collaborative Environmental Governance: Achieving Collective Action in Social-Ecological Systems." *Science* 357 (6352): eaan1114.
- Bodin, Örjan, Steven M Alexander, Jacopo Baggio, Michele L Barnes, Ramiro Berardo, Graeme S Cumming, Laura E Dee, et al. 2019. "Improving Network Approaches to the Study of Complex Social–Ecological Interdependencies." *Nature Sustainability* 2 (7): 551–59.
- Bodin, Örjan, Michele L Barnes, Ryan RJ McAllister, Juan Carlos Rocha, and Angela M Guerrero. 2017. "Social–Ecological Network Approaches in Interdisciplinary Research: A Response to Bohan et al. and Dee et Al." *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 32 (8): 547–49.
- Bodin, Örjan, Garry Robins, Ryan RJ McAllister, Angela M Guerrero, Beatrice Crona, Maria Tengö, and Mark Lubell. 2016. "Theorizing Benefits and Constraints in Collaborative Environmental Governance: A Transdisciplinary Social-Ecological Network Approach for Empirical Investigations." *Ecology and Society* 21 (1).
- Bodin, Örjan, and Maria Tengö. 2012. "Disentangling Intangible Social–Ecological Systems." *Global Environmental Change* 22 (2): 430–39.
- Bruceckner-Irwin, Irene, Derek Armitage, and Simon Courtenay. 2019. "Applying a Social-Ecological Well-Being Approach to Enhance Opportunities for Marine Protected Area Governance." *Ecology and Society* 24 (3).

- Charles, Anthony, Laura Loucks, Fikret Berkes, and Derek Armitage. 2020. "Community Science: A Typology and Its Implications for Governance of Social-Ecological Systems." *Environmental Science & Policy* 106: 77–86.
- Clement, Floriane. 2013. "For Critical Social-Ecological System Studies: Integrating Power and Discourses to Move beyond the Right Institutional Fit." *Environmental Conservation* 40 (1): 1–4.
- Dressel, Sabrina, Göran Ericsson, and Camilla Sandström. 2018. "Mapping Social-Ecological Systems to Understand the Challenges Underlying Wildlife Management." *Environmental Science & Policy* 84: 105–12.
- Enqvist, Johan P, Maria Tengö, and Örjan Bodin. 2020. "Are Bottom-up Approaches Good for Promoting Social–Ecological Fit in Urban Landscapes?" *Ambio* 49: 49–61.
- Epstein, Graham, Jeremy Pittman, Steven M Alexander, Samantha Berdej, Thomas Dyck, Ursula Kreitmair, Kaitlyn J Rathwell, Sergio Villamayor-Tomas, Jessica Vogt, and Derek Armitage. 2015. "Institutional Fit and the Sustainability of Social–Ecological Systems." *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* 14: 34–40.
- Fleischman, Forrest, Natalie Ban, Louisa Evans, Graham Epstein, Gustavo Garcia-Lopez, and Sergio Villamayor-Tomas. 2014. "Governing Large-Scale Social-Ecological Systems: Lessons from Five Cases." *International Journal of the Commons* 8 (2).
- Folke, Carl. 2006. "Resilience: The Emergence of a Perspective for Social–Ecological Systems Analyses." *Global Environmental Change* 16 (3): 253–67.
- Garmestani, Ahjond S, and Melinda Harm Benson. 2013. "A Framework for Resilience-Based Governance of Social-Ecological Systems." *Ecology and Society* 18 (1).
- Guerrero, Angela M, Nathan J Bennett, Kerrie A Wilson, Neil Carter, David Gill, Morena Mills, Christopher D Ives, et al. 2018. "Achieving the Promise of Integration in Social-Ecological Research." *Ecology and Society* 23 (3).
- Guerrero, Angela M, Örjan Bodin, Ryan RJ McAllister, and Kerrie A Wilson. 2015. "Achieving Social-Ecological Fit through Bottom-up Collaborative Governance: An Empirical Investigation." *Ecology and Society* 20 (4).
- Herrfahrdt-Pähle, Elke, and Claudia Pahl-Wostl. 2012. "Continuity and Change in Social-Ecological Systems: The Role of Institutional Resilience." *Ecology and Society* 17 (2).
- Hohbein, Rhianna R, Nathan P Nibbelink, and Robert J Cooper. 2021. "Non-Governmental Organizations Improve the Social-Ecological Fit of Institutions Conserving the Andean Bear in Colombia." *Ecology & Society* 26 (4).
- Hukkinen, Janne I. 2012. "Fit in the Body: Matching Embodied Cognition with Social-Ecological Systems." *Ecology and Society* 17 (4).
- Janssen, Marco A, and Elinor Ostrom. 2006. "Governing Social-Ecological Systems." *Handbook of Computational Economics* 2: 1465–1509.
- Kofinas, Gary P. 2009. "Adaptive Co-Management in Social-Ecological Governance." *Principles of Ecosystem Stewardship: Resilience-Based Natural Resource Management in a Changing World*, 77–101.
- Lebel, Louis, John M Anderies, Bruce Campbell, Carl Folke, Steve Hatfield-Dodds, Terry P Hughes, and James Wilson. 2006. "Governance and the Capacity to Manage Resilience in Regional Social-Ecological Systems." *Ecology and Society* 11 (1).
- McGlynn, Bridget, Ryan Plummer, Angela M Guerrero, and Julia Baird. 2023. "Assessing Social-Ecological Fit of Flood Planning Governance." *Ecology and Society* 28 (1): Article-number.
- Moss, Timothy. 2012. "Spatial Fit, from Panacea to Practice: Implementing the EU Water Framework Directive." *Ecology and Society* 17 (3).

- Nuss, Henry J, Donna L Williams, Jennifer Hayden, and Colleen R Huard. 2012. "Applying the Social Ecological Model to Evaluate a Demonstration Colorectal Cancer Screening Program in Louisiana." *Journal of Health Care for the Poor and Underserved* 23 (3): 1026–35.
- Olsson, Per, and Victor Galaz. 2012. "Social-Ecological Innovation and Transformation." In *Social Innovation: Blurring Boundaries to Reconfigure Markets*, 223–47. Springer.
- Parke, Belinda, and Neena L Chappell. 2010. "Transactions between Older People and the Hospital Environment: A Social Ecological Analysis." *Journal of Aging Studies* 24 (2): 115–24.
- Pittman, Jeremy, and Derek Armitage. 2017. "How Does Network Governance Affect Social-Ecological Fit across the Land–Sea Interface? An Empirical Assessment from the Lesser Antilles." *Ecology and Society* 22 (4).
- Poorten, Brett T van, Robert Arlinghaus, Katrin Daedlow, and Susanne S Haertel-Borer. 2011. "Social-Ecological Interactions, Management Panaceas, and the Future of Wild Fish Populations." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 108 (30): 12554–59.
- Robards, Martin David, and Amy Lauren Lovecraft. 2010. "Evaluating Comanagement for Social-Ecological Fit: Indigenous Priorities and Agency Mandates for Pacific Walrus." *Policy Studies Journal* 38 (2): 257–79.
- Rosenschöld, Johan Munck af, and Peeter Vihma. 2022. "Achieving Social-Ecological Fit in Projectified Environmental Governance: Exploring Vertical and Horizontal Dimensions." *Environmental Science & Policy* 136: 127–35.
- Sayles, Jesse S, and Jacopo A Baggio. 2017. "Social–Ecological Network Analysis of Scale Mismatches in Estuary Watershed Restoration." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 114 (10): E1776–85.
- Sayles, Jesse S, Maria Mancilla Garcia, M Hamilton, Steven M Alexander, Jacopo A Baggio, AP Fischer, Karin Ingold, Genevive R Meredith, and Jeremy Pittman. 2019. "Social-Ecological Network Analysis for Sustainability Sciences: A Systematic Review and Innovative Research Agenda for the Future." *Environmental Research Letters* 14 (9): 093003.
- Shogren, Karrie A. 2013. "A Social–Ecological Analysis of the Self-Determination Literature." *Mental Retardation* 51 (6): 496–511.
- Steelman, Toddi. 2016. "US Wildfire Governance as Social-Ecological Problem." *Ecology and Society* 21 (4).
- Sternlieb, Faith, R Patrick Bixler, Heidi Huber-Stearns, and others. 2013. "A Question of Fit: Reflections on Boundaries, Organizations and Social–Ecological Systems." *Journal of Environmental Management* 130: 117–25.
- Stokols, Daniel. 2000. "The Social Ecological Paradigm of Wellness Promotion." *Promoting Human Wellness: New Frontiers for Research, Practice, and Policy*, 21–37.
- Van Riper, Carena J, Andreas Thiel, Marianne Penker, Michael Braitto, Adam C Landon, Jennifer M Thomsen, and Catherine M Tucker. 2018. "Incorporating Multilevel Values into the Social-Ecological Systems Framework." *Ecology and Society* 23 (3).
- Vantaggiato, Francesca, Mark Lubell, Michelle Hummel, Aaron CH Chow, and Alain Tcheukam Siwe. 2023. "Creating Adaptive Social-Ecological Fit: The Role of Regional Actors in the Governance of Sea-Level Rise Adaptation in San Francisco Bay." *Global Environmental Change* 80: 102654.
- Wandel, Johanna, and Gregory P Marchildon. 2010. "Institutional Fit and Interplay in a Dryland Agricultural Social–Ecological System in Alberta, Canada." *Adaptive Capacity and Environmental Governance*, 179–95.

- Wang, Shuai, Shuang Song, Junze Zhang, Xutong Wu, and Bojie Fu. 2021. "Achieving a Fit between Social and Ecological Systems in Drylands for Sustainability." *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* 48: 53–58.
- Wijermans, Nanda, Geeske Scholz, Émile Chappin, Alison Heppenstall, Tatiana Filatova, J Gareth Polhill, Christina Semeniuk, and Frithjof Stöppler. 2023. "Agent Decision-Making: The Elephant in the Room-Enabling the Justification of Decision Model Fit in Social-Ecological Models." *Environmental Modelling & Software* 170: 105850.